

The New Headway Course book Review

Evrin Sencar

MA TESOL, Seinan Gakuin University

ABSTRACT

The New Headway pre-intermediate is still one of the most preferred course books by many language schools all around the world. Part of the reason is that it's regarded as one of the most easily adaptable course books to diverse socio-cultural contexts. Cunningsworth (1995) argued that course books should correspond to learners' needs. they should match the aims and objectives of the language learning program. However, there is no course book can be absolutely ideal for a particular group of learners. Each group of learners has its own needs and reasons to study a language and language teachers should choose suitable materials that best suit the learners' needs in terms of the purpose of the course, learners' language proficiency, learners' learning styles and the aim of the materials. Does the New Headway pre-intermediate fulfill this aim? This assignment addresses the need for adapting course book materials in group classes and discusses the importance of other surrounding factors for effective learning and teaching, such as course book design, flexibility, authenticity in texts, learner engagement and integrated skills.

Keywords: Authenticity, coursebooks, Headway, flexibility, learner engagement

Description of the Course Book

The New Headway Pre-intermediate course book mainly aims to balance communicative and traditional approaches. The course book is based on a structural syllabus, yet it still includes task-based activities mainly focusing on practice and the use of language rather than linguistic forms. Activities range from controlled to free tasks and aims to both allow learners to freely express themselves and provide them with adequate practice and drills. The course book is divided into 14 chapters and every chapter is organized around a theme. the name of the chapter is given on each chapter, which usually includes the theme of the chapter, followed by broad categories, namely, "Language input," "Grammar," "Vocabulary," and "Everyday English" are headings under those key items from the unit are listed. Under "skills development", a breakdown is given of reading, speaking, listening, and writing. The exercises and page numbers relevant to those skills are also provided.

It usually takes a long process and all-out effort to write and publish a course book which can cater the needs of a wide range of learners and teachers. Publishers and writers need to take various important factors into account to meet those needs. However, we should never neglect the sales aspect. We may all agree that publishers would only invest if they found it worth. Therefore, plenty of market research is done before a course book is published to determine the needs and interests of users. However, whether course books can absolutely meet the needs of learners or not still remains as a question. Therefore, teachers are expected to fulfill this aim and they are given a crucial role to make the most of a course book (Deci et al., 1992; Egitim, 2020; Tomlinson, 2014).

Adapting Materials

Even in these days of on-line and technologically driven learning, the most widely used aid in the classroom, after the board, is still the course book (Egitim & Price, 2020). A significant part of many lessons around the world involves the teacher and students doing exercises or tackling reading or listening material from their course book. Publishers recognize this, of course, and continue to invest significant amounts of money in new materials and - sometimes - earn huge amounts of money back. However, is it realistically possible to expect publishers to publish a course book that can correspond to the needs of learners from diverse socio-cultural backgrounds? Mishan (2005) pointed out that published materials of any kind have to cater for a very wide range of possible users, which means that they cannot address any individual or group of students directly. " The improbability of designing a course book that can meet the needs of different socio-cultural environments sometimes leads to a tendency for over-reliance on course books with non-realistic expectations made of them in English language teaching. Some teachers regard course books as immutable and mythical objects and tend to teach the course book itself rather than use it as a resource for creativity and inspiration and a tool for their learners. After all, course books can be static objects, organized on traditional syllabus lines which may not be appropriate for individual classes and students.

Perhaps the issue is not so much whether or not course books are 'a good idea', but rather how they are used. Cunningsworth (1995) suggested that teachers, with direct personal knowledge of their classroom teaching, should see

textbooks as their servants instead of masters as a resource or an ideas bank which can stimulate teachers' own creative potential. Tomlinson (2014) suggested that perception of relevance and utility can be achieved by relating teaching points to interesting and challenging classroom tasks and by presenting them in ways which could facilitate the achievement of task outcomes desired by learners. In the hands of creative and humanizing teachers and their students, any static object -a course book, magazine, novel, website can be transformed into an effective learning tool. Adapting materials allows teachers to achieve more compatibility and fitness between the textbook and the teaching environment and maximize the value of the book for the benefit of their particular learners and for the most effective teaching outcomes to achieve. It would consequently lead to the improvement of the textbook in the sense of being able to suit the particular situation and empowering and reskilling the teachers (Egitim, 2017; Sucháňová, 2020).

As we touched on before, it wouldn't be thoroughly realistic to expect publishers to publish a course book that can correspond to the needs of all the learners of diverse socio-cultural backgrounds. However, it can be achieved by producing locally adapted materials mainly focusing on the target learners' interests and what they really want to learn the language for which can encourage intellectual, aesthetic and emotional involvement that will maximize learning potential. Most teachers recognize the need to make their learners aware of the potential relevance and utility of the language and skills they are teaching. Relating course book activities to learners interests and to real life tasks which the learners may need to perform in the target language can be deemed as an effective way to acquire language. However, when teachers adapt course book activities to their classroom situations, it's important that teachers should take certain factors into account to better correspond to the diverse needs of their learners.

Flexibility

In recent years Materials development has been greatly underscored in ELT field since selection and organization of materials may considerably affect the way of teaching and learning specially in a rather course book-centered curriculum. In Istanbul, Turkey, English teaching is generally course book centered and course books are treated as courses and both teachers and students rely heavily on them. Finishing the course books rather than learning English in a more interactive and communicative way seems to be the interest of most students and teachers and even the final goal of most courses.

The new headway series, which claim to advocate communicative language teaching and provide a learner-centered approach, seem to be the most common selection of the English language schools in all around the world. Communicative language teaching stresses learners' needs and mainly focuses on providing enough flexibility and responsiveness to individuals' needs. Although most course books have fine design of learning activities and appealing layout, they are most likely to decide the learning needs beforehand and leave only little room for flexibility and creativity that teachers need to better personalize their lesson activities to meet the particular needs of their learners. Most course books have a comparatively low degree of flexibility to satisfy the diverse needs of potential users in various contexts, which is not learner-centered in its real sense is in conflict with the principles of communicative language teaching.

Flexibility is a key demand in a learning centered curriculum in order to address the individuals' learning needs, to facilitate negotiated interaction between participants and to maximize learning potential in the communicative classroom activities. New headway pre-intermediate course book can partially achieve this aim because of its structural yet functional syllabus that consists of range of practice tasks based on wide-ranging communicative contexts which allow students to think and make their own findings in the language. Especially the starter section of each chapter includes small bits of exercises which are to introduce the language points covered on each chapter. The exercises include matching questions and answers, completing sentences and various games that urge the learners to draw on their own experiences and make their own discoveries in the language.

The course book also includes large scale images on each chapter which sometimes fills the whole page. Those pictures are perhaps designed to raise learners' language awareness and to allow teachers to create more engaging and personalized classroom activities which can stimulate active learning. For instance, when we look at the new Headway Pre-intermediate course book chapter four, we can see a big image where there are two women in the kitchen talking about shopping and there is also a shopping list given on top of the image. We can easily adapt this image with a bit of effort and creativity to various effective classroom activities which can engage students and raise their interest in the language. such as make your own shopping list and discuss what you need and what you don't with your friend, what things did you buy when you last went shopping and what not.

The course book also provides very clear headings and signposting by means of its structural syllabus which makes it very easy for students to find their ways around on each chapter. However, this raises the question of whether teachers and learners should rely heavily on a course book or not. The course book emphasizes the importance of grammar and vocabulary in language teaching and learning therefore it provides a wide variety of language practice tasks incorporating all four skills. It's true that integrated activities designed to develop all four skills in the classroom help

learners do real things outside. The new headway pre-intermediate course book provides long tape scripts and sequenced listening and grammar drills. Those long listening and grammar-based activities are mainly comprised of topics that are irrelevant to students' learning goals and interest, and they restrict teachers' flexibility to create more engaging and creative classroom activities. It's important that teachers should feel they could move activities around, cut them out or supplement them according to the needs of their learners.

Authenticity in Texts

Historically Materials development and syllabus design are largely dependent on the arrangement of materials and activities rather than authenticity. In other words, the main concern is how the content is arranged and organized rather than what it contains is relevant and interesting to a wide range of learners, teachers and classroom contexts. Most course books mainly provide teachers and learners with a range of professionally developed materials within tried and tested syllabus structures to allow teachers to spend their valuable time more on facilitating learning and to help learners more easily keep track of course book activities. Course books also include specially contrived texts to simplify activities for diverse levels of learners to ensure that learning aim is achievable.

However, these aims could turn teaching and learning into an artificial and wearisome process which may lead to loss of motivation and interest in using course books. Therefore, materials should, one would hope, be interesting in its own right – its content stimulating, informative and realistic to create a genuine learning environment for learners which will also enable teachers to promote a more effective learning and therefore get better results. Not only that, if course book writers could somehow convince learners that by using the course book, they would learn some English but, in a wider sense they will improve their overall communication skills, and be entertained at the same time, more authenticity would be in greater demand in course book activities.

Authentic materials are usually superior in relevance to learners' lives. They offer a real situation of language use. Thus, in recent years, the number of teachers who agree with using authentic texts in classrooms has dramatically increased because of the need for more stimulating, motivating and realistic activities to create a more effective learning environment for their learners and to have them experience the real world of the language. However, when and to what degree we can introduce authentic texts still remains as a question. Students would want material that could enjoy and in which they could find things they could identify with and learn from. Language needed to be comprehensible but there did need to be 'new' language there on page. (Tomlinson, 2014) In that respect the new headway pre-intermediate course book activities comprise of both authentic and specially contrived texts which the authors tried to simplify activities to match the levels of learners and also introduce authentic language to have learners experience the language used in real world.

During the course book activities speaking and vocabulary exercises such as "Starter, fill in the blanks, Practice and Everyday English" are generally more simplified compared to the main reading and listening activities which are mainly long and contain more authentic language because of the functional yet structural syllabus of the course book that activities on each chapter unfold from less complex to longer and more challenging structures towards the end of each chapter.

During a class assessment of one of the newly hired teachers in a language school in Istanbul, I observed that a fill in the blanks activity in the course book mainly designed to introduce the past simple and past continuous tenses was found too difficult by most of the students. (New Headway pre-intermediate, page 24, chapter 3- newspaper stories) However the next two activities (discussing grammar and fortunately/unfortunately- page 25) that focus on the same language points were found more engaging and therefore more effective by the same group of students. Although newspaper stories contained more authentic language, they were thoroughly irrelevant to most students. During the activities "Discussing grammar and Fortunately/Unfortunately" the students could find things that are relevant to their own lives and were given more opportunities to make their own discoveries in the language which helped them develop a better understanding of the target language points. When we look at the main reading and listening activities of each chapter, we can also notice that a great deal of authentic language was used to stimulate language awareness and introduce students to the language used in the real world (Egitim, 2018).

However, some of the reading and listening activities in the course book may sometimes fail to serve this purpose as they can be deemed too long, challenging and more importantly irrelevant to learners of diverse cultural backgrounds. The kind of long reading and listening activities may also lead to loss of concentration and interest. During another assessment of a newly hired teacher's class in Istanbul, I observed a teacher having to play the same tape script five times as the activity failed to stimulate learners' interest and build the desired level of understanding of the language. (New Headway pre-intermediate tape script 11.3) Although the long listening activity was quite informative and contained a great deal of authentic language, it wasn't found relevant and interesting for most of the students where as a reading activity about a footballer and a pop star in the New Headway Pre-intermediate(page 58) managed to arouse different groups of students' interest as they could easily relate the couple to the celebrities they admire in real life and

therefore the activity better aid their learning and helped them acquire the authentic language in the text. A modern course book like new headway pre-intermediate while still a very British book, is much less exclusively located in Britain. In many course books a shift to international settings reflects, no doubt, a growing sense on the part of the publishers of English as an increasingly global language. (Globalization and language teaching-David Block and Deborah Cameron-157).

Therefore, when designing course books, it would be important to mention that publishers and writers should primarily focus on meeting the needs of a wide variety of learners and course book activities should be designed to stimulate learners' interest and should allow enough room for learners to make their own discoveries in the language. It's obviously important to meet the needs of teachers as well. If teachers are not enthused by materials their dissatisfaction is always apparent to the learners, the materials lose credibility and the learners' motivation and investment of energy are reduced (Tomlinson, 2014)

Course Book Activities and Learners Engagement

Learners' engagement is a significant element of language acquisition and it's usually deemed as one of the most challenging tasks for all teachers. Teachers usually deal with a wide variety of learners with different needs and interests and one thing we know about language acquisition is that most learners only learn what they need and want to learn. Tomlinson (2014) suggests that "Providing opportunities to learn the language needed to participate in an interesting activity is much more likely to be profitable than teaching something because it is the next teaching point in the syllabus.

Most course books today come with a similar syllabus design, layout and limited teaching situations that are mostly irrelevant to learners as the aim is to meet the general needs of a wide range of students, teachers and classroom contexts. Thus, teachers generally face a big challenge to prepare interesting and relevant activities for their learners. Obviously as we discussed the importance of adapting materials, we often emphasized that it's part of teachers' responsibility to make their classroom activities interesting and relevant to their learners. However, we also believe that if course books can partially share this responsibility, they could provide teachers with substantial aid to make their class activities more engaging and relevant for their learners. The New Headway pre-intermediate course book stands out among the other recently published course books in terms of its approaches to learner engagement.

It's true that Headway's structural yet functional syllabus mainly consists of activities that are mainly designed to encourage learners to discover language points themselves. Task-based activities in the syllabus serve as a warm-up and an exposure to the target language points. They allow learners to share their own experiences with other learners and therefore stimulate communicative interaction that helps teachers to create an ideal learning environment for their learners. The types of activities included as follows:

- Starter section- it's a personalized activity designed to encourage students to expose themselves to the target language points.
- Practice section- it consists of a number of personalized activities that require students to complete certain sentence patterns, fill in the blanks or talk about themselves using the target language points.
- Everyday English- it's aimed to design to expose learners to more authentic language such as idioms, phrasal verbs and natural phrases and usually serves as the final application to the language of each chapter.

Exercises in the new Headway pre-intermediate are mostly based on present, practice and produce paradigm and has a strong emphasis on grammar which is usually deemed as a necessary aspect of language acquisition by most learners. In the New Headway pre-intermediate, learners are expected to work out the grammar rules for themselves and build a certain analytic knowledge through this systematic process. However, this kind of analytic knowledge is not available in unplanned discourse and may not thoroughly helpful with learners to effectively communicate their ideas. As the knowledge is gained through without any experience of real life or things that are relevant to learners, they may fail to choose the appropriate responses required in those situations. Situation or task-based role plays are quite effective to work on this particular skill as They allow plenty of grammar applications to real life situations in which students could easily relate to things that they experience in their own lives, which helps them acquire the ability to use the language and also ease the process of language acquisition (Egitim, 2020).

Integrated Skills

To build better awareness of the language in learners, teachers sometimes need to expose their learners to real life situations where all four skills are used in conjunction. This doesn't only help learners to tackle the problems of real life but also help them become communicatively more competent. Language use is a combined skill where everything depends on everything else -at the very least we listen and speak together, and read and write together (Tomlinson, 2014). The four skills of the English language are clearly dependent on each other in natural discourse. For instance, a text has to be written down before people can read it just as speaking and listening take place in conversations together.

Therefore, a course book should not only represent the flexibility of the English language by presenting it in different situations. It must also demonstrate how language can be used in both productive (speaking and writing) and receptive (listening and reading) skills (Egitim, 2018). New Headway stands out with its approach to encourage the development of both oral and aural communication skills including a number of listening activities per unit, reading comprehensions, grammar writing exercises and discussion opportunities. Usually, activities range from very controlled to freer tasks which allow learners to practice the language adequately and apply it to their own life situations.

One other benefit of practicing a language through an integrated and communicative fashion is that it enables learners to work on all four skills at the same time and helps them strike a good balance between all four skills. Most may agree that the new Headway pre-intermediate has a very strict focus on listening and grammar although I still think that speaking and writing exercises in the book are all sufficient. From my experiences with a number of classes, most students in that level showed certain capability of grammar and listening thus they could easily cope with the kinds of exercises the book provides. However, they were mostly weak on certain conversation skills such as giving opinions, making simple arguments, suggestions and so on. Thus, one may feel that the course book lacks in providing enough activities to work on those conversation skills which would help learners become communicatively more competent (Gilmore, 2008; Gorsuch, 2001; Hyland, 2006).

CONCLUSION

Firstly, Course books should allow enough flexibility for teachers to move activities around, cut them out or supplement them according to the needs in order to provide the learners with better personalized activities. Secondly, Course books should expose learners to the necessary variety of situations in which physical setting prescribes the language the learners are likely to need outside the classroom. (eg, letters and emails [Unit2], descriptive pieces [Unit6], biographies [Unit10]) can consume, often involving activities that are more appropriate for homework. All four skills, however, must be practiced and assessed in class and, although writing is often perceived as the most difficult of the four, its development is essential in everyday life (Egitim, 2017).

By separating writing, its removal from the classroom is almost being endorsed, a move that would disadvantage visual learners, discourage students with learning difficulties and fail to thoroughly train students. In general, however, the skills are adequately represented (short sentence writing is a regular feature), but, as pointed out by Cunningsworth (1995) noted that in actual language, we rarely use one skill in isolation. Numerous other communicative situations in real life involve integrating two or more of the four skills (Mishan, 2005). Integrating skills is promoted throughout the course, such as pair work discussion of grammar activities includes listening, speaking, reading, and writing, asking students to write questions in pairs from a text uses all four skills. Communicative interactions between students will strengthen their cognitive strategies and teach them how to deal with the problem of real-time responses and unpredictability in normal conversation (Egitim & Price, 2020).

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